

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 20

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 20:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 21:1 לַמְנַצֵּחַ מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד : 2</p>
<p>Psa. 20:1 May the LORD answer you in the day of trouble!</p>	<p>יְהוָה בְּעֵזֶךָ יִשְׁמַח־מֶלֶךְ וּבִישׁוּעַתְךָ מִהַיְגִיל [הַיְגִיל]</p>
<p>May the ^bname of the ‘God of Jacob set you <i>securely</i> on high!</p>	<p>מֵאֵד : 3 תֵּאֲנוֹת לְבוֹ נִתְתָּה לּוֹ</p>
<p>² May He send you help ^afrom the sanctuary</p>	<p>וְאֶרְשֵׁת שְׁפָתָיו בְּל־מִנְעֵת</p>
<p>And ^bsupport you from Zion!</p>	<p>סֵלָה : 4 כִּי־תִקְדָּמוּנוּ בְּרִכּוֹת</p>
<p>³ May He ^aremember all your meal offerings</p>	<p>טוֹב תִּשִׁית לְרֵאשִׁי עֲטֹרַת פָּז : 5</p>
<p>And ^bfind your burnt offering ¹acceptable! ²Selah.</p>	<p>תִּיִּים אִשָּׂאֵל מִמֶּךָ נִתְתָּה לּוֹ</p>
<p>Psa. 20:4 May He grant you your ^aheart's desire</p>	<p>אֶרֶךְ יָמִים עוֹלָם וָעֶד : 6 נִדְוָל</p>
<p>And ^bfulfill all your ¹counsel!</p>	<p>כְּבוֹדוֹ בִישׁוּעַתְךָ תוֹד וְהִדָּר</p>
<p>⁵ ¹We will ^asing for joy over your ²victory,</p>	<p>תִּשְׁנֶה עָלָיו : 7 כִּי־תִשִׁיתָהוּ</p>
<p>And in the name of our God we will ^bset up our banners.</p>	<p>בְּרִכּוֹת לָעֵד תִּתְּיָהוּ בְשִׁמְחָה</p>
<p>May the LORD ^afulfill all your petitions.</p>	<p>אֶת־פְּנִיךָ : 8 כִּי־הֶמְלִיךְ בְּטִיחַ</p>
<p>Psa. 20:6 Now ^aI know that the LORD saves His anointed;</p>	<p>בֵּיתוֹהָ וּבְתֹסֵד עֲלִיּוֹן בְּל־</p>
<p>He will ^banswer him from His holy heaven</p>	<p>יִמּוּט : 9 תִּמְצָא יָדְךָ לְכָל־</p>
<p>With the ^{1c}saving strength of His right hand.</p>	<p>אֵיבֶיךָ יִמְיִיךָ תִּמְצָא שְׂנֵאִיךָ : 10</p>
<p>⁷ Some ¹boast in chariots and some in ^ahorses,</p>	<p>תִּשִׁיתָמוּ אֶשׁ לְעֵת</p>
<p>But ^bwe ²will boast in the name of the LORD, our God.</p>	<p>פְּנִיךָ יְהוָה בְּאִפּוֹ יִבְלָעֵם</p>
<p>⁸ They have ^abowed down and fallen,</p>	<p>וְתִאֲכַלֵּם אֵשׁ : 11 בְּרִימוֹ מֵאֶרֶץ</p>
	<p>תִּאֲבֹד אוֹזְרֵם מִבְּנֵי אָדָם : 12</p>
	<p>כִּי־נָטוּ עָלֶיךָ רֵעָה חֲשָׁבוּ מְזֻמָּה בְּל־יִוָּכְלוּ : 13 כִּי</p>
	<p>תִּשִׁיתָמוּ שְׁכֵם בְּמִיתָרֶיךָ תִּכּוֹנֵן</p>

But we have ^brisen and stood upright.
⁹ ^{1a}Save, O LORD;
May the ^bKing answer us in the day we call.

עַל־פְּנֵיהֶם : 14 רִוְמָה יְהוָה
בְּעֵינֶיךָ נִשְׁרָה וְנִזְמָרָה
גְּבוּרָתְךָ :

References

<p>Psalm 20:1 ^aPs 50:15 ^bPs 91:14 ^cPs 46:7, 11</p> <p>Psalm 20:2 ^aPs 3:4 ^bPs 110:2</p> <p>Psalm 20:3 ¹Lit <i>fat</i> ²<i>Selah</i> may mean: <i>Pause, Crescendo</i> or <i>Musical interlude</i> ^aActs 10:4 ^bPs 51:19</p> <p>Psalm 20:4 ¹Or <i>purpose</i> ^aPs 21:2 ^bPs 145:19</p> <p>Psalm 20:5 ¹Or <i>Let us sing</i> ²Or <i>salvation</i> ^aPs 9:14 ^bPs 60:4 ^c1 Sam 1:17</p> <p>Psalm 20:6 ¹Or <i>mighty deeds of the victory of His right hand</i> ^aPs 41:11 ^bIs 58:9 ^cPs 28:8</p>	<p>Psalm 20:7 ¹Or praise <i>chariots</i>, or trust, or are strong <i>through</i> ²Lit <i>make mention of; or praise the name</i> ^aPs 33:17 ^b2 Chr 32:8</p> <p>Psalm 20:8 ^aIs 2:11, 17 ^bPs 37:24; Mic 7:8</p> <p>Psalm 20:9 ¹Or <i>O LORD</i>, save the king; answer us ^aPs 3:7 ^bPs 17:6</p>
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Targum

Psa. 20:1 For praise; a psalm of David. ² May the LORD receive your prayer in the day of trouble, may the name of the God of Jacob lift you up. ³ May he send your help from his sanctuary, and from Zion give you aid. ⁴ May he remember all your offerings, and may your whole-offerings drip with fat forever. ⁵ May he give you according to your desires, and may he fulfill all your counsel. ⁶ Your people will say, "Let us give praise for your redemption, and in the name of our God we will be mustered; may the LORD fulfill all your requests." ⁷ Now I know that the LORD has redeemed his anointed; he has accepted his prayer from his holy dwelling in the heavens; in might is the redemption of his right hand. ⁸ Some by chariots, and some by horses, but we will swear by the name of the LORD our God. ⁹ They have stooped and fallen, but we have remained upright and become strong. ¹⁰ O LORD, redeem us, mighty king, accept our prayer in the day we call out.

Spiritual Analysis

The spiritual rewrites for the verses are in bold.

Introduction

This Psalm is the response of the people of Israel to Psalm 19. In that Psalm, David expressed his loyalty to the LORD's Law. The Psalm is addressed to David, proclaiming that they too have come to understand his relationship with the LORD. They wish to offer him their sentiments of loyalty and affection.

Superscript

לְמַנְצֵחַ (lam'nazecha) – the English translations of this Psalm like to use the phrase "for the choir director," however this translation is inaccurate. The "Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament" indicates that this translation is far from correct. A proper translation is "To Netzach." The Sefirah Netzach offers victory when its light is placed upon a person. The implication is that the people are happy that David had so many military victories. When David was victorious, the people were protected and prospered. The people are offering this prayer about David and their allegiance to him and the Sefirot Netzach.

To the Sefirot Netzach, a psalm of David.

Verse One

The "day of trouble" is a time of dire circumstances of inevitable disaster. Jacob is called out because every time it appeared that Jacob was in the day of trouble, the

LORD saved him. The LORD will protect and assist any person who upholds the Laws and Mitzvot of the Torah.

The LORD will answer you in the days of trouble; the name of the God of Jacob will raise you on high.

Verse Two

It is believed that our spiritual foundation and strength come to humans through Mount Zion, the location of the LORD's Temple. The Zohar speaks about places on the Earth where the goodness of the Sefirot flows into Malchut (our realm). One of these places is Mount Zion in Israel. There are other locations around the world. However, the most active place is Mount Zion. The help and support from Zion are to help each of us to come closer to the LORD.

Your spiritual help will come from His Sanctuary, and spiritual strength to resist evil will come from Zion.

Verse Three

The meal offering is symbolic of the joy of life, thus symbolizing a person's entire fate. It can be said that this offering is giving back to the LORD some of the joys and blessings that have been bestowed. By doing this, the person demonstrates their dependence on the LORD. The burnt offerings are another example of an understanding of the blessings from the LORD.

The LORD will accept your offerings of homage and will always find your offerings, your thanksgiving, acceptable. Meditate on this verse.

Verse Four

The people are saying to David that they will lay down all desires to what the LORD wants. They saw how David reacted to the LORD and tried to live a life worthy of the LORD's name. In return, the LORD gave David all of his heart's desires.

May the LORD give you everything your heart desires and always be your guide in life.

Verse Five

The people rejoiced because David the Sefirot Netzach showered him with blessings. They set up banners that allowed them to rally around the various blessings. Therefore, the banners represented each blessing.

We will shout for joy every time Netzach blesses you by rallying around your banner in the name of the LORD; may Netzach fulfill all your desires through victory.

Verse Six

The people saw that the LORD was with David throughout his troubles and triumphs. Even when David sinned, the LORD was with him. The LORD gave David a method to offer repentance. The people experienced the LORD with David.

Now I have come to know that the LORD has granted happiness to his appointed king (David); He will always hear you and will answer you from the Heavens and his acts of salvation of His right hand will sustain you.

Verse Seven

The people will always remember the LORD by His holy name. Other nations know their god in chariots and horse. Israel will not worship material things as the LORD.

Other nations see their god in chariots and others in horses, but for us, we remember our LORD by His holy name.

Verse Eight

The other nations who celebrate their god have fallen and stayed down while we have always risen and stood upright because the LORD is our God and takes care of His children.

When other nations fell, not to rise again, we have fallen, but the LORD raises us, and we will stay risen.

Verse Nine

The people's confidence was in the Divine aid that the LORD offered, and the people will always consider the LORD a king.

May the LORD grant salvation to his people. The King God will answer us on the days which we call upon Him.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirot Netzach, a psalm of David.

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Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

